

SECTION OF BIOLOGY AND ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES

PROVISION OF ALTERNATIVE ENERGY TO THE SETTLEMENTS OF THE KARABAKH ECONOMIC REGION OF THE AZERBAIJAN REPUBLIC

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Abstract

The results of research on assessing the potential for the development of alternative energy sources in the territory of the settlements of the Karabakh economic region of the Republic of Azerbaijan are presented in this paper. In modern times, the problem of creating "green zones" has become one of the most important problems in almost all countries of the world. The depletion of hydrocarbon reserves, the sharp rise in the cost of hydrocarbon fuels, the deterioration of the environment, the increase in the average temperature of the atmosphere - all these factors have led to the fact that the expansion of "green zones" and the creation of new sources of renewable energy are under the supervision of the UN. For this region, the most promising energy sources are hydroelectric power plants, solar and solar thermal stations, wind farms and bio-organic fuel installations.

Keywords: hydrocarbon fuel, alternative, energy sources, hydroelectric power station, solar station, wind station.

Introduction.

Despite the fact that Azerbaijan is rich in energy resources and is known as an exporter of hydrocarbon energy resources in the world, the use of renewable energy sources has always been in the spotlight. In order to develop the field of renewable energy in Azerbaijan, relevant laws and regulations have been adopted. In recent years, the work carried out in this area has been continued, and the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan No. 339-VIQ dated May 31, 2021 "On the use of renewable energy sources in the production of electricity" pays special attention to the contribution to the development of renewable energy. In order to ensure the application and implementation of the law, the implementation of relevant measures in the direction of the preparation of by-laws continues.

Paragraph 5 of the document "Azerbaijan 2030: National Priorities for Socio-Economic Development", approved by the Edict of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated February 2, 2021 ("Clean Environment" and "Green Growth of the Country"), indicates the directions for counteraction to climate change, as well as issues of application renewable energy on the principles of green energy space in all sectors of the economy. Thus, in accordance with the priorities of the socio-economic development of the country, in the current and future period, more and more attention is paid to the use of renewable energy sources and the expansion of the use of "green" technologies. As part of the ongoing work in this area, research has continued throughout the country in the direction of identifying areas with high potential for renewable energy sources. National priorities are also of particular importance towards realizing the commitments stemming from the UN's "Transforming Our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development".

The purpose of this paper is to study the potential of alternative energy sources in to provide the settlements of the Karabakh economic region of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

Estimates of the powers of various alternative energy sources by region.

The conducted research and data analysis showed that the total electricity capacity of Azerbaijan is 7542.2 MW, the capacity of renewable energy power plants, including large hydroelectric power plants, is 1304.5 MW, which is 17.3% of the total capacity. The hydro-power capacity is 1154.8 MW (30 stations, 20 small hydropower plants), the wind power capacity is 66.1 MW (7 stations, 2 hybrid), the bioenergy power capacity is 37.7 MW (2 stations, 1 hybrid), the solar power capacity is 45.9 MW (12 stations, 2 hybrid). The devices based on wind with 2.7 MW power, the solar station with 3 MW power and the bioenergy power with 0.7 MW were installed at one hybrid power plant (Gobustan). The installed capacity of renewable energy sources, excluding large hydropower plants, in 2021 amounted to 194 MW power, which is 2.5% of the total electricity generation capacity.

During 2021, electricity generation in Azerbaijan amounted to 27.8 billion kWh. During this period, electricity generation at fuel-burning power plants amounted to 26.2 billion kWh, at hydroelectric power stations - 1277.3 million kWh. and 339.9 million kWh from other sources. During the year, 91.5 million kWh were received. from wind power plants, 55.2 million kWh from solar power plants, 193.2 million kWh of electricity was produced at the solid waste incineration plant. Electricity generated from renewable energy sources accounted for approximately 5.8% of total production.

Work on the assessment of the possible potential for electricity production from renewable energy sources and steps is very important [1-4]. In the direction of identifying areas with high potential for renewable energy sources, 8 directions were selected. Appropriate measures are already being taken to implement pilot projects in 3 selected areas. Compared to wind energy, in the coming years it is planned to implement

projects in the regions to use the potential of solar energy, use land unsuitable for agriculture, and distribute power generation from renewable energy sources.

As a contribution to global climate change mitigation initiatives, Azerbaijan has set a goal of maintaining a 35% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 2030 compared to the base year (1990). In November 2021, at the COP26 conference held in Glasgow, our country made a new commitment to reduce emissions by 40% by 2050 and create a "net zero emission" zone in territories of Karabakh economic region. To achieve these goals, the Ministry of Energy has set the main goal of increasing the share of investments in renewable energy in the country's total energy balance to 30% by 2030. To this end, it is planned to create 1500 MW power of new generating capacities from renewable energy sources, including 440 MW power in 2023, 460 MW power in 2023-2025, and 600 MW power in 2026-2030.

On January 9, 2020, the Executive Agreements on the implementation of pilot renewable energy projects between the Ministry of Energy and "ACWA Power" companies of Saudi Arabia and Masdar of the United Arab Emirates were signed in the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan. In accordance with the agreements, pilot projects are planned in the Republic of Azerbaijan for the construction of wind power plants with a capacity of 240 MW power with ACWA Power and solar power plants with a capacity of 230 MW power with Masdar.

On December 30, 2020, between the Ministry of Energy, Azerenergy public corporation and "ACWA Power", an enforceable "Investment Agreement", "Energy Purchase and Sale Agreement" and "Transmission Network Connection Agreement" for the planned wind station project were signed. "Khizi-Absheron" with a capacity of 240 MW power on April 6, 2021, the Ministry of Energy and Azerenerji OJSC and the Masdar company of the United Arab Emirates signed "Investment agreement", "Energy purchase agreement" and "Grid connection agreement" for the 230 MW solar power plant project.

In order to ensure the fulfillment of the tasks set by the Edict of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On accelerating reforms in the energy sector of the Republic of Azerbaijan" dated May 29, 2019 No. 1209, in order to create new production energy capacities in the field of renewable energy in the country and to attract private, including foreign investments in the sphere, Worldwide cooperation is being carried out with the International Finance Corporation, which is part of the International Bank Group, on the preparation of the Roadmap for the Development of Offshore Wind Energy in Azerbaijan. On 04/14/2021, the "Memorandum of Understanding on Cooperation in the Field of Offshore Wind Energy Use between the Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the International Finance Corporation (IFC)" and work on the development of the mentioned roadmap continues was signed.

According to the Paris Agreement adopted at the 21st Conference of the Parties on December 12, 2015,

the Republic of Azerbaijan submitted its nationally determined contributions to the Convention Secretariat. As a contribution to initiatives to mitigate the effects of global climate change, Azerbaijan has set a goal of maintaining a 35% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 2030 compared to the base year (1990). In November 2021, at the COP26 Conference held in Glasgow, our country accepted a new commitment to reduce emissions by 40% by 2050 and to create a "net zero emission" zone in the Karabakh economic region territories. In order to achieve these goals, the Ministry of Energy has set the main goal of increasing the share of renewable energy investment in the total energy balance of the country to 30% by 2030. For this purpose, owing to renewable energy sources, it is planned to create 1500 MW of new generation power capacities, including 440 MW in 2023, 460 MW in 2023-2025, and 600 MW in 2026-2030.

Under the Asian Development Bank-supported "Knowledge Sharing and Technical Assistance Support for the Development of a Floating Solar panels" Pilot Project, installation of a 100 kW photovoltaic power system on Lake Buyukshor, as well as building business models to encourage private sector participation in the installation solar power stations, training tools designed to strengthen national capacity. The project is scheduled to be completed by March 2023.

On May 3, 2021, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev signed the Edict "On measures related to the creation of the Green Energy Zone in the Karabakh economic region territories of the Republic of Azerbaijan". An agreement was signed between the Ministry of Energy and the Japanese company "TEPCO" in order to attract a specialized international consulting company to implement the tasks arising from the order, as well as to create a "Green Energy Zone" in the Karabakh economic region territories. During the relevant period, the activities envisaged under the contract were implemented, resulting in the preparation of a Concept Paper for the establishment of a "Green Energy Zone".

In the concept, models of regional development were developed using various scenarios, energy needs were predicted based on the growth rate of gross domestic product and population resettlement scenarios, and various options for energy supply were evaluated. At the same time, work continues towards the preparation of the General Plan. In order to study the potential of solar, wind, biomass, thermal, geothermal and other renewable energy sources in the territory of the settlements of the Karabakh economic region of the Republic of Azerbaijan, to determine the coordinates of the regions, as well as to use the available resources, wind and solar power plants, as well as research in the direction of ensuring energy supply through the construction of hydroelectric power stations on reservoirs, lakes, and small rivers.

About 25% of Azerbaijan's internal water resources are formed in these territories, which is approximately 2.56 billion m³ per year. In particular, it should be noted that there is a favorable potential for the implementation of solar energy projects in the Karabakh

economic region territories. Thus, solar radiation observed in Zangilan, Jabrayil, Gubadli and Fizuli is the second most favorable region of the country after solar radiation observed in Nakhchivan region. As a result of preliminary observations, the corresponding areas with favorable solar radiation power were identified.

The potential of solar energy power in the territories of the Karabakh economic region is estimated at more than 7200 MW. Based on preliminary studies, a comparative analysis of topography, climatic conditions, proximity to power grids, energy production potential, transport infrastructure and other technical factors, the territory of the Jabrayil and Zangilan regions was recognized as suitable for solar energy projects.

Based on preliminary studies, it was established that there is a favorable wind potential in these territories, especially in the mountainous regions of Lachin and Kalbajar. The analysis shows that the wind energy potential in these areas is about 2000 MW. In previous years, relevant scientific studies were carried out on the availability of geothermal energy sources. Geothermal energy is mainly used for electricity generation (at a favorable temperature and discharge), heat supply and tourism and balneological purposes. Preliminary analyzes show the presence of geothermal sources in the mountainous part of the Lesser Caucasus (4000-5000 m³/day (30-74°C)). According to preliminary observations, it is more expedient to use this potential for heating and balneological purposes, respectively.

The hydropower resource potential of Azerbaijan is 16 billion kWh power. According to the State Statistics Committee of Azerbaijan, in 2016, the installed capacity of the country's power plants amounted to 7300 MW, including 1100 MW of the capacity of hydroelectric power plants. The share of hydroelectric power stations in electricity generation is more than 8%. According to forecasts, the production of hydroelectric power by 2025 will be 4.6 billion kWh power. The largest hydroelectric power plants in Azerbaijan are the Mingechevir hydroelectric power station (capacity 400 MW power) and the Shamkir hydroelectric power station (capacity 380 MW power).

The results of the investigations and discussion.

Thus, it can be noted that Azerbaijan is one of the countries with a high potential for renewable energy sources. The potential of economically viable and technically suitable renewable energy sources in our country is 27000 MW, including:

- 3000 MW of wind energy power;
- 23000 MW of solar energy power;
- bioenergy potential 380 MW energy power;
- the potential of mountain rivers is estimated at 520 MW energy power.

As part of the implementation of the task of creating a "Green Energy Zone", in order to study the potential of solar, wind, biomass, thermal, geothermal and

other renewable energy sources in the Karabakh economic region to determine the coordinates of the regions, as well as to use available resources, wind and solar power plants, the research is being carried out in the direction of ensuring energy supply through the construction of hydroelectric power stations on reservoirs, lakes, and small rivers.

Conclusion

Thus, on the basis of the conducted research, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Approximately 25% of Azerbaijan's inland water resources are formed on the territory of Karabakh, which is approximately 2.56 billion m³ per year.

2. Solar radiation observed in Zangilan, Jabrayil, Gubadli, Fizuli and Aghdam regions is the second most favorable region of the country after solar radiation observed in Nakhchivan region. The potential of solar energy in the Karabakh territories is estimated at more than 7200 MW power. Based on preliminary studies, a comparative analysis of topography, climatic conditions, proximity to power grids, energy production potential, transport infrastructure and other technical factors, the territory of the Jabrayil and Zangilan regions was recognized as suitable for solar energy projects.

3. The presence of favorable wind potential in the mountainous regions of Lachin and Kalbajar has been established on the basis of preliminary studies. The analysis shows that the wind energy potential in these areas is about 2000 MW power.

4. In previous years, relevant scientific studies were carried out on the availability of geothermal energy sources in these areas. Geothermal energy is mainly used for electricity generation (if the temperature and water discharge are favorable) and for thermal energy production. Preliminary analyzes show the presence of geothermal sources in the mountainous part of the Lesser Caucasus (water discharge is 4000-5000 m³/day and 30-74°C). According to preliminary observations, it is more expedient to use this potential to provide heat.

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